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ANALELE ȘTIINȚIFICE
ALE
UNIVERSITĂȚII „ALEXANDRU IOAN CUZA”
DIN IAȘI
(SERIE NOUĂ)

ISTORIE

TOM LXV
2019

Editura Universității „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași

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The noble heraldry of the pre-modern Moldavia***

The present study regards a period considered for a long time as a decline in the Romanian history: the age when the princes that came from Phanar – the Greek vicinity of Istanbul – occupied the thrones of the Principalities of Moldavia and Wallachia (that is to say the core of today's Romania), has been eventually reconsidered as an age of cultural and social progress, and also as a time of deep economic transformation¹.

Since the founding of the two Principalities in the 14th century, the Romanian noble class continued to exist until its legal dissolution, as an effect of the 1858 *Convention of Paris*². The Moldavian noble class of the Phanariot age was an elite formed by people having prestige and social influence and owing their administrative power to the proximity to the ruler and to their genealogical connections³. Consequently, having a personal function was defining for belonging

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*** This work is based upon the paper lectured at the XXIth Colloquium of the International Academy of Heraldry (Anvers/Antwerp, 18-20 September 2019). The authors avail themselves of this opportunity to express their sincere thanks to Mrs. Delia Bălăican (Bucharest) and to Messrs. Drăgan-George Basarabă (Timișoara), Sorin Iftimi (Iași) and Lucian-Valeriu Lefter (Vaslui), for the valuable assistance they have offered while completing this text.

¹ Andrei Pippidi, *Phanar, phanariotes, phanariotisme*, in *RESEE*, XIII (1975), 2, p. 237-238.

² Art. 46, alin. (6) of the *Convention of Paris*, issued on 7/19 August 1858, abolished all the class privileges of the two Principalities – Ion Ionașcu, Petre Bărbulescu, Gheorghe Gheorghe, *Relațiile internaționale ale României în documente (1368-1900). Culegere selectivă de tratate, acorduri, convenții și alte acte cu caracter internațional*, București, 1971, p. 342.

³ Cristian Ploscaru, Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *The study of the boyar elite from the Romanian Principalities (eighteenth century). Methodological approach*, in *NORDSCI. International Conference on Social Sciences, 19-23 august 2019, Conference Proceedings*, book 1, vol. 2, Sofia, 2019, p. 131.

to the noble class of the 17th-18th centuries; *lato sensu*, all the landowners pertained to the same social category⁴.

The use of arms by the local nobility – the boyars – originated in the late 14th century, the oldest documents issued by the Moldavian chancellery being authenticated, besides the princely seal, with the armorial seals of several barons of the realm⁵. Known particularly through its use upon seals and reaching its peak during the long reign of prince Stephen the Great⁶ (1457-1504) but re-enforced one century later, under prince Peter the Lame⁷, both times deeply influenced by the Polish armorial tradition, the noble heraldry known three periods, as defined in 1977 by the regretted Dr. Dan Cernovodeanu: the ‘classic age’ (14th-16th centuries), the ‘middle age’ (16th-18th centuries), and the ‘modern age’ (18th-19th centuries)⁸ – the last two overlapping with the period approached in our study.

The premises at the base of the local heraldry were quite different to what were the beginnings of the heraldic phenomenon in Western and Central Europe. Apparently, the coats of arms had no military purposes (apart from their use on flags)⁹, no jousting or tournaments were recorded and no institution exercised the power of granting or recording arms¹⁰. At some point of its social, political, and cultural development, the local Moldavian noble class started to use coats of arms, following the examples of the neighbouring, Western-influenced elites depending on the Hungarian and the Polish-Lithuanian crowns. There are even testimonies about educated people cherishing their noble identity, as it was an unnamed Moldavian inhabitant, mentioned in the souvenirs of Jacques Moreau de Brasey (1663-1723) – the so-called “count of Lion en Beauce”, a French adventurer who served Peter the Great by the time of the 1711 Pruth River Campaign – Moldavian

⁴ Lucian-Valeriu Lefter, *Începuturile boierimii Moldovei. Document și istoriografie*, in *Familiiile boierești din Moldova și Țara Românească. Enciclopedie istorică, genealogică și biografică*, coordonator and coauthor Mihai Dim. Sturdza, vol. V, Ceaur-Cuza, București, 2018, p. 36-37.

⁵ Leon Șimanschi, *Cele mai vechi sigilii domnești și boierești din Moldova (1387-1421)*, in *AIIAI*, XVII (1980), p. 143-146. Also, Tudor-Radu Tiron, *At the Border between Two Worlds. Hungarian and Polish Influences upon the Walachian and Moldavian Medieval Heraldry (Fourteenth – Sixteenth centuries)*, in “*Genealogica & Heraldica. Grenzen in Genealogie en Heraldiek/Frontiers in Genealogy and Heraldry / Frontières dans la Généalogie et l’Héraldique*, Handelingen van het XXX^e Internationale Congres der Genealogische en Heraldische Wetenschappen / Proceedings of the XXXth International Congress of Genealogical and Heraldic Sciences / Actes du XXX^e Congrès International des Sciences généalogique et héraldique”, Maastricht, 24-28 septembrie 2012, ’s-Gravenhage, Stichting De Nederlandse Leeuw, 2014, p. 349-350.

⁶ Tudor-Radu Tiron, Lucian-Valeriu Lefter, *Sigiliile boierilor lui Ștefan cel Mare*, in *AP*, XI (2015), 1, p. 175-206.

⁷ Petronel Zahariuc, *Observații asupra unor sigilii medievale moldovenești (I)*, in *ArhGen*, IV (IX) (1997), 1-2, p. 258-259.

⁸ Dan Cernovodeanu, *Știința și arta heraldică în România*, București, 1977, p. 165-175.

⁹ Silviu Andrieș-Tabac, *Despre steagul lui Ștefan cel Mare purtat în ziua de 12 septembrie 1485 la Colomeea în cadrul ceremoniei de depunere a omagiului de vasalitate față de regele Poloniei Cazimir IV Jagiello*, in *HM*, I, 2018, p. 61-65, 67-68.

¹⁰ Ștefan S. Gorovei, *Cu privire la heraldica medievală românească*, in *ArhGen*, II (VII) (1995), 1-2, p. 273.

who proudly pretended to have a noble ancestry and a coat of arms¹¹: “...Le même Moldave (...) se vantâ d’être noble de sang, & d’armes...”¹². On the other hand, the so-called Phanariots – that is to say the oligarchy originated from Phanar, who exercised the upper civil and ecclesiastical functions – were very fond of their blood and cultural connections with the Byzantine world¹³, as well as of their part to the governance of the Ottoman Empire¹⁴, despite their lack of cohesion¹⁵. For a family who gained some fortune, it was a great temptation to publicly express its social success by symbolic acts such as donating to the Holy Land or the Holy Mountain Athos, or obtaining burial places in some much-frequented church. Preserving the family’s memory – “for remembrance” – was a keystone in the thinking of the Phanariot noble class, the heraldic image fulfilling this purpose. An example is the coat of arms rendered upon the richly-decorated tombstone from the cathedral of the Bishopric of Roman, erected upon the grave of a certain Nicolaos (†1735), the young descendant of a Constantinopolitan family¹⁶ (**Fig. 1**).

Fig. 1.

A considerable number of Phanariot families, which gave dignitaries and even princes to the Romanian Principalities, used coats of arms: the Argyropoulos¹⁷, the Balassakis¹⁸, the Caradjas¹⁹, the Catacazis²⁰, the Chrisoscoleos²¹, the

¹¹ *Călători străini despre Țările Române*, vol. VIII, Maria Holban, M. M. Alexandrescu-Dersca Bulgaru, Paul Cernovodeanu (editors), București, 1983, p. 459-462, 475.

¹² *Memoires politiques, amusans et satiriques, de messire J. N. D. B. C. de L., colonel du Regiment de Dragons de Casanski & Brigadier des Armées de Sa M. Czarienne*, tome premier, Veritopolie, MDCCXVI, p. 58-59.

¹³ Andrei Pippidi, *op. cit.*, p. 234-235, 237.

¹⁴ Mihai Dim. Sturdza, *Dictionnaire Historique et Généalogique des Grandes Familles de Grèce, d’Albanie et de Constantinople*, 2^e édition, Paris, 1999, p. 134, 146.

¹⁵ Socrate C. Zervos, *Recherches sur les Phanariotes: à propos de leur sentiment d’appartenance au même groupe social*, in *RESEE*, XXVII (1989), 4, p. 307-311.

¹⁶ N. Iorga, *Inscripții din bisericile României*, vol. II, București, 1908, p. 19.

¹⁷ Mihai Dimitri Sturdza, *op. cit.*, p. 215-216.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 222.

¹⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 257-258.

²⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 265.

Handjerys²², the Logothetis²³, the Manos²⁴, the Mavrocordatos²⁵ etc. Known notably from Eugène Rizo-Rangabé's genealogical works²⁶, the heraldic achievements of these lineages have been rarely approached by the literature of the last century²⁷. In most cases, we can only presume that the coats of arms associated with these families were actually in use in the timelines of our study, despite the appearance of these achievements, which is clearly of the late 19th century – the early 20th century. However, we are aware of some instances in which the heraldic continuity is clear enough, as is the case of the Mavrocordatos family, whose coat of arms dates as back as the 17th century (as attested by the roll of the Greek students of the University of Padua)²⁸, being subsequently transformed and included in the arms accompanying the engraved portrait of prince Alexander Mavrocordat 'Firaris' (1785-1786)²⁹, and publicly displayed upon the entrance tower of St Spyridon monastery of Iași (1786)³⁰.

Coats of arms connected with the Phanariot families may also appear in sources which are exceeding the timelines of our study, or have nothing to do with the area of the Moldavian Principality. A good example is offered by the achievement of Grigore Buzoianu (Hrisoscoleu/Chrisoscoleo), carved upon the 1833 commemorative inscription of the Church of the Dormition of Our Lady of Câmpina, in Wallachia. Coming from a lineage already illustrated in Moldova, by Iordachi Hrisoscoleu (who was great *ușier* in 1711), by Ianachi I Hrisoscoleu (who was great *postelnic* in 1747) and by Aristarchi Hrisoscoleu (who had an interesting career, up to great *vistiernic*, before dying in 1758)³¹, Grigore Buzoianu used a very interesting shield (quarterly with a central inescutcheon) (**Fig. 2**), whose elements seem to concentrate several ancestral heraldic traditions. Even if the meaning of this achievement remains inexplicable, it is in all appearances fitting within the timelines and the region approached by the present study.

²¹ *Ibidem*, p. 267.

²² *Ibidem*, p. 300-301.

²³ *Ibidem*, p. 307-308.

²⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 313-314.

²⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 319-328.

²⁶ Eugène Rizo-Rangabé, *Livre d'or de la noblesse phanariote en Grèce, en Roumanie, en Russie et en Turquie*, Athènes, Imprimerie S. C. Vlastos, 1892 and idem, *Livre d'or de la noblesse phanariote et des familles princières de Valachie et de Moldavie*, Imprimerie S. C. Vlastos, 1904.

²⁷ Antoine Jérôme Delenda, Jean Typaldos-Lascaratos, *L'héraldique en Grèce*, in "Comunicaciones al XV Congreso Internacional de las Ciencias Genealógica y Heráldica, Madrid, 19-25 septiembre 1982. Volumen oficial", Madrid, Instituto Salazar y Castro (C.S.I.C.), 1983, p. 568.

²⁸ Mihai Dimitri Sturdza, *op. cit.*, p. 63, 73 (fig. 3).

²⁹ Maria Dogaru, *Un armorial românesc din 1813. Spița de neam a familiei Balș dotată cu steme*, București, 1981, p. 34-35 and fig. 8.

³⁰ Sorin Iftimi, *Cercetări privitoare la istoria bisericilor ieșene. Monumente, ctitori, mentalități*, Iași, 2014, p. 116-117, 314.

³¹ Mihai Dimitri Sturdza, *op. cit.*, p. 267.

Fig. 2.

Unfortunately, the information regarding the coats of arms of families equally having foreign roots is quite small. The researchers are aware of the typical coats of arms of the lineages bearing Polish names, achievements which are largely met with the heraldic work of Traian Larionescu³². The information is however fragmentary: for instance, we know that there was a Polish family Kazimir of the Herb Biberstein, of which presumably descended a homonymous boyar family, attested in Moldavia since 1662³³, and we also know that this Moldavian family used a variant of this coat of arms, as proven by a 19th century seal-matrix³⁴. Does it mean that this lineage conserved the same coat of arms, from more than a century and a half? Or it is about an achievement assumed during the time of the Romantic genealogical researches, as is the case with other boyar families? The same dilemma stands in the case of the Moldavian immemorial families claiming the right to display Polish arms; for instance, the boyars Gane traditionally pretended to have arms – Herb Rawicz – established before the end of the 18th century³⁵, however recent analysis clarify the issue, proposing the mid-19th century, as a much more reasonable moment of adopting this coat of arms (in connection with the efforts of the family to compile its pedigree)³⁶. Besides the arms of families having Phanariot and Polish roots, there are very few examples of foreign achievements connected with the Moldavian territory in the timelines of our study; the most known example is the coat of arms of Manuc Bey (Emanuel Mârzayan), the wealthy “Prince of the Armenians”, carved upon his 1817 funeral stone (the grave was initially placed at Manuc’s estate of Hâncești, în Bessarabia, then moved to the Armenian Church of Chișinău). Still unexplained by the literature, the unusual shield of Manuc was placed upon a mantle having a princely crown,

³² Traian Larionescu, *Armorialul Moldovei de Sus*, București, 1976, *passim*.

³³ Gheorghe G. Bezviconi, *Boierimea Moldovei dintre Prut și Nistru. Actele Comisiei pentru cercetarea documentelor nobilimii din Basarabia, la 1821*, București, 1940, p. 80.

³⁴ Sorin Iftimi, *Vechile blazoane vorbesc. Obiecte armoriata din colecțiile ieșene*, Iași, 2014, p. 149 and fig. 5.

³⁵ Constantin Gane, *Pe aripa vremii*, București, 1923, p. 100-101.

³⁶ Ștefan S. Gorovei (editor), *C. Gane: însemnări genealogice inedite*, in „Prutul. Revistă de cultură”, s.n., anul VIII (XVII) (2018), 2 (62), p.182-183.

alluding the title of “prince of Moldavia” conferred to him in 1808 by sultan Mahmud II³⁷.

The predominant part of noble Moldavian heraldry consists of **self-assumed arms**. This long-term characteristic applies also to our interspace, the examples of achievements conferred to the inhabitants of the Principality being extremely rare – as it was the coat of arms given on 18 November 1790 by Leopold II, Holy Roman emperor, to Matthias Philadelphi, “...Civitatis Iassi in Moldavia Physici...”, for the medical services rendered to the Imperial and Royal army during the Austro-Turkish War (1788-1791) – the composition obviously featuring the vision of the Habsburg’s chancellery (**Fig. 3**)³⁸.

Fig. 3.

A special situation regards the coats of arms belonging to the Moldavian elites of Bukovina and Bessarabia – regions that passed under the rule of the Habsburgs (in 1774), respectively the Romanovs (in 1812). (On the other hand, the arms of the boyar families settled to the Russian Empire after the 1711 defeat of the

³⁷ Silviu Andrieș-Tabac, *Noile simboluri heraldice ale municipiului Hâncești*, in “Simpozion de numismatică organizat în memoria martirilor de la Valea Albă, la împlinirea a 525 de ani (1476-2001), Chișinău, 13-15 mai 2001”, București, 2001, p. 269-271 and fig. 7-8. The shield depicts a tree (apple or orange?), issuing from a terrace, with a lion couchant guardant upon the latter, accompanied in sinister by a six-rays star and a faced moon turned to dexter.

³⁸ Mihail G. Stephănescu, Jean N. Mănescu, *Enluminures héraldiques des XVI^e-XVIII^e siècles dans la collection de l'Académie Roumaine*, in *RRHA-BA*, tom XVII (1980), p. 39-40. The diploma is conserved at the Library of the Romanian Academy, *Manuscrite*, P. 570. More on the foreign noble titles conferred upon the Moldavian and Walachian boyars at Dan Cernovodeanu, *Evoluția armeriilor Țărilor Române de la apariția lor și până în zilele noastre (sec. XIII-XX)*, Brăila, 2005, p. 275-276.

Russian-Moldavian army at the Battle of Stănilești, such as Bantăș-Kamensky, Kulikovsky, Vremev etc.³⁹, as well as the arms attributed to other prominent figures, such as the one received in 1796 by the *hatman* Ilie Catargi, who became a State Advisor to the empress Catherine the Great⁴⁰, are not a part of the present analysis, as belonging to the Russian heraldic system.) In most of the situations, the specialist is aware only about the late official versions of such coats of arms, which origins coincide with the timelines of our study or are even earlier. This was the instance of the arms of the hereditary knights Onciul from Bukovina, known from a 1906 official record (Fig. 4), where was mentioned that the four petitioners were allowed to use the achievement of their ancestor, living in the 18th century⁴¹; this was also the instance of the coat of arms of the hereditary nobles Gore from Bessarabia, approved by the tsar on 15 November 1906 (Fig. 5)⁴², but based on a 17th century Transylvanian grant of arms⁴³. In both mentioned instances, the use of arms by the 18th century members of the families Onciul and Gore is reasonably supposable⁴⁴.

Fig. 4.

Fig. 5.

³⁹ Jean Nicolas Mănescu, *Eléments d'héraldique roumaine dans l'armorial russe*, in "Recueil du XV^e Congrès International des Sciences Généalogiques et Héraldiques", Madrid, 19-25 septembre 1982, Tom. I, Madrid, 1983, p. 5-23; see also Tudor-Radu Tiron, Lucian-Valeriu Lefter, *Genealogic and Heraldic Notes on the Moldavian Families Settled in the East (15th – 18th Centuries)*, in *CI*, XXXIV (2015), p. 109-136.

⁴⁰ Gheorghe G. Bezviconi, *op. cit.*, p. 188-189. See also Silviu Andrieș-Tabac, *Stema rusească a familiei Catargi și stema familiei Cristi*, lecture given at the XVth National Congress of Genealogy and Heraldry, Iași, 13-15 May 2010.

⁴¹ Teodor Bălan, *Familia Onciul – Studii și documente*, Cernăuți, 1927, p. 210-213, nr. 178-179 (certificate of the Austrian Minister of Home Affairs of 29 March 1906).

⁴² *Общій гербовникъ дворянскихъ родовъ всероссійскія имперіи*, XVIII, 1908, nr. 30. The official certificate is conserved at Serviciul Județean Iași al Arhivelor Naționale, *Colecția Stampe și Fotografii*, nr. 763.

⁴³ More about at Silviu Andrieș-Tabac, *Paul Gore heraldist*, in *ArhGen*, IV (IX) (1997), 1-2, p. 234-235.

⁴⁴ Dan Cernovodeanu, *Evoluția...*, p. 305-307 (noble families of Bukovina), 307-310 (noble families of Bessarabia). Regarding the coats of arms of the Moldavian nobles of Bukovina, the author mentioned that many of these were self-assumed.

Only a small number of the Moldavian noble families received armorial letters patent before the timelines of our study, making then efforts to conceive and obtain official registrations from authorities of other countries, which usually dealt with such cases. An example is the achievement of the Hâjdeu family, conferred on 4 February 1676 by John III Sobieski, king of Poland and grand duke of Lithuania, to the Moldavian *armaș* Gheorghe Hâjdău⁴⁵; the branch settled in Galicia obtained in 1782 the recognition of its noble status, also composing a revised and expanded version of the patrilineal arms, also reflecting the alliance with the family of Stephen Petriceicu, prince of Moldavia⁴⁶ (Fig. 6 and 7).

Fig. 6.

Fig. 7.

Another example refers to the arms of Sturdza family, conferred to Ilie Sturdza by Michael Apaffy, prince of Transylvania, on 24 February 1679; the original diploma – today lost – is known through a 1795 copy, artistically transcribed in Czernowits, outside the Moldavian frontiers of the period (Fig. 8)⁴⁷.

Fig. 8.

⁴⁵ Costin Feneșan, *Diplomele de indigenat polon ale boierilor moldoveni Grigore Hăbășescu și Gheorghe Hâjdău*, in *ArhGen*, IV (IX) (1997), 3-4, p. 93-97, 98-101 and fig. 2-3.

⁴⁶ The great *paharnic* Stephen (Ștefan) Hâjdău, George's brother, was married with Alexandra, prince Petriceicu's sister – Costin Feneșan, *op. cit.*, p. 98-99. See, idem, *Indigenatul austriac al familiei nobiliare Hâjdău*, in *ArchM*, IV (2012), p. 30 and fig. 1.

⁴⁷ Cristian Popișteanu, Dorin Matei, *Sturdzeștii. Din cronica unei familii istorice*, foreword by Acad. Dan Berindei, [București], 1995, p. 167-170.

Even if the family used, for generations, a completely different, self-assumed coat of arms (**Fig. 9**)⁴⁸, the conferred coat of arms was equally used, for instance in the heraldic seal of the *vornic* Constantin Sturdza, in 1818 (**Fig. 10**)⁴⁹.

Fig. 9.

Fig. 10.

It is relevant to notice that it was the 1679 symbol of the Sturdza family which was combined with the Moldavian auroch, when members of this lineage occupied the throne of the Principality (1822-1828 and 1834-1849) (**Fig. 11 and 12**)⁵⁰, this demonstrating that the family gave pre-eminence to the arms legally attributed by a *fons honorum*, to the detriment of the self-assumed achievement.

Fig. 11.

Fig. 12.

⁴⁸ Alexandre A. C. Sturdza, *Règne de Michel Sturdza, Prince régnant de Moldavie, 1834-1849. Précédé d'un exposé historique des événements de 1821 à 1834, et suivi d'un aperçu historique sur les événements de 1849 à 1859, d'actes et documents diplomatiques inédits*, Paris, 1907, fig. 47 (1615 seal impression of the great *hatman* Ion Sturza), 49 (1737 seal impression of the great *logofăt* Sandul Sturza), 50 (seal matrix dated 1779).

⁴⁹ BAR, *Documente istorice*, IV/80 (document of 18 September 1818).

⁵⁰ Laurențiu-Ștefan Szemkovicș, Maria Dogaru, *Tezaur sfragistic românesc. II. Sigiliile emise de cancelaria domnească a Moldovei (1387-1856)*, București, 2006, p. 85-86 and fig. 256-259.

The local use of coats of arms reflected a pragmatic vision: **the coats of arms were used with a purpose**. The arms were used as *signs of land property*, as well as for the *ecclesiastical patronage*. Both instances were connected with the wealthiest noble Moldavian families, having the conscience of their social position and also knowing where to find the gifted artist – into a time of extreme political and social instability, when investments in this kind of art were hazardous! Consequently, there are very few examples to mention here: as a sign of soil ownership – the stone-carved double-headed eagle of the great *logofăt* Iordache Cantacuzino-Deleanu (1688-1758), once displayed at this family’s estate of Deleni and unfortunately disappeared today (**Fig. 13**)⁵¹; as a sign of noble patronage of a church – the achievements of the same family, placed in the decoration of several churches, an eloquent example being the 1722 commemorative inscription of the monument of Deleni (**Fig. 14**)⁵².

Fig. 13.

Fig. 14.

Frequently met with the Western and Central European heraldry, the coats of arms used as a *funeral decoration* were quite rare in Moldavia; the tombstones were still tributary to Oriental patterns, where the place for the inscription and the vegetal decoration leaves little place for a personal symbol of the deceased. Among the few known examples is the tombstone of the great *logofăt* Constantin Ghica († 1818), from St Spyridon church of Iași (**Fig. 15**)⁵³, the one of the *hatman* and *logofăt* Neculai Stratulat (1763-1818) from the old Metropolitan church of Iași (**Fig. 16**).

⁵¹ Tudor-Radu Tiron, *O stemă cantacuzină la conacul din Deleni (Iași)*, in *Familii boierești din Moldova și Țara Românească. Enciclopedie istorică, genealogică și biografică*, coordonator and coauthor Mihai Dim. Sturdza, vol. III. Familia Cantacuzino, București, 2014, p. 400-401 (drawing by Tudor-Radu Tiron).

⁵² Mihai-Bogdan Atanasiu, *Patrimoniul heraldic în familia Cantacuzinilor moldoveni*, in *OI*, VII₂ (2006), p. 99-100.

⁵³ Sorin Iftimi, *Turnul bisericii Sfântul Spiridon din Iași, un monument între două lumi*, in *Orașul din spațiul românesc între Orient și Occident. Tranziția de la medievalitate la modernitate*, Laurențiu Rădvan (editor), Iași, 2007, p. 179.

Fig. 15.

Fig. 16.

The main use of coats of arms was connected with *the validation of documents*, the armorial bearings being constantly displayed, at all times, upon seals. Even if the noble class of the Romanian Principalities knew different ways to seal a document – with antique (or antique-like) mythological gems (Fig. 17 – example from a 1747 document, issued by Tofana daughter of Necolai Bașotă, ex-great *vistier*)⁵⁴, with initials and monograms (Fig. 18 – example from a 1794 document, issued by the *postelnic* Toader Năstase)⁵⁵, with coins and even with fingers (for the illiterate subjects) (Fig. 19 – example from a 1717 document)⁵⁶ – coats of arms constantly decorated the seals.

Fig. 17.

Fig. 18.

Fig. 19.

⁵⁴ BAR, *Documente istorice*, XXXIII/30 (document of 23 March 1747).

⁵⁵ BAR, *Documente istorice*, CXXXI/19 (document of 30 April 1794).

⁵⁶ BAR, *Documente istorice*, VIII/45 (document of 2 December 1717).

However, the use of seals should be understood the ‘elastic’ way. In the Romanian Principalities, like everywhere else, the seals were used *ad validitatem*: the documents should have seal impressions, attesting the wish of each subject. A step forward was to introduce elements reflecting his identity: inscription, initials, coat of arms, even portrait⁵⁷. On the other hand, we should not forget that most of the seals were seal rings, that is to say precious artefacts that can change the owner. The temptation of using a ‘nicer’ seal-ring, even newly crafted, was great, for people less accustomed with the good heraldic practices. Therefore, the heraldic usage suffered from the point of view of consistency, with curious instances probably unknown in the rest of the continent. An example taken from the genealogical researches, is the series of heraldic seals used by the *vornic de poartă* Neculai Tiron (cca. 1737-1760), a typical member of the Moldavian little noble class of the mid-18th century. No less than four different heraldic types were associated with him between 1744 and 1758 (**Fig. 20**)⁵⁸, the latter being close if not identical with the 1767 seal impression of a contemporary, a certain Constantin Donici, apparently unrelated to him⁵⁹.

Fig. 20

The reasons why choosing a seal or another varied. For instance, a certain Gheorghe, son of Tănase Pahonie, sealed a document in 1765, with a matrix bearing a coat of arms displaying an equestrian image of St George; however, the presence of someone else’s initials testimonies that the seal-matrix was not made for him, but simply used by him (**Fig. 21**)⁶⁰.

⁵⁷ More on this latter type at Emil Virtosu, *Din sigilografia Moldovei și a Țării Românești*, in *DIR*, Introducere, vol. II, 1956, p. 501-504.

⁵⁸ Tudor-Radu Tiron, *Pe urmele strămoșilor. Fragmente istorice despre Tironeștii din ținutul Vasluiului*, in „Prutul. Revistă de cultură”, s.n., anul VIII (XVII) (2018), 2 (62), p. 112-114 and fig. 19 (the seal impressions reproduced in this study appear upon the documents dated 17 August 1744, 2 May 1750, 1 August 1752 and 22 July 1758).

⁵⁹ Lucian-Valeriu Lefter, *Contribuții la istoria familiei Donici. Avatarurile unei căsătorii: Scarlat Donici și Smaranda Roset*, in *Retrospecții medievale. In honorem Professoris emeriti Ioan Caproșu*, editors Victor Spinei, Laurențiu Rădvan, Arcadie M. Bodale, Iași, 2014, p. 402, fig. 2.

⁶⁰ BAR, *Documente istorice*, CIII/139 (document of 18 November 1765).

Fig. 21.

On the other hand, there were also instances in which the heraldic identity of a lineage was more seriously followed, notably for the noble families better placed in the Moldavian hierarchy. One of the best examples is the 17th – 18th century series of seals of the Cantacuzino family, equally featuring the traditional double-headed eagle of Byzantine roots (Fig. 22)⁶¹.

Fig. 22.

⁶¹ Petronel Zahariuc, *op. cit.*, p. 264-266. Covering almost 150 years of Moldavian sphragistics, the seals reproduced here pertained to: 1. Iordache Cantacuzino (11 March 1640), 2. Toma Cantacuzino (6 December 1638), 3. Iordache Cantacuzino (25 January 1630), 4. Iordache Cantacuzino (11 March 1640), 5. Iordache Cantacuzino (17 September 1656), 6. Toderașco Iordache Cantacuzino (25 January 1655), 7. Toderașco Iordache Cantacuzino (8 October 1658), 8. Iordache Cantacuzino Pașcanu (2 June 1722), 9. Ecaterina Cantacuzino (1 September 1759-31 August 1760), 10. Ioan Cantacuzino (1 September 1759-31 August 1760) and 11. Enache Cantacuzino (5 August 1781).

Such ideal cases are however rare, and there is nothing uncommon to see that different generations of the same blood using distinct heraldic achievements; the best example is perhaps the noble family Miclescu, of which we know the 1786 heraldic seal of the *căminar* Iordache Miclescu (*1756 – †?) (Fig. 23)⁶², this composition was replaced four decades later by another one, completely different and reflecting the vision that the family had about its own genealogy (Fig. 24)⁶³.

Fig. 23.

Fig. 24.

Besides the use of arms as signs of signs of land property, ecclesiastical patronage, for funeral purposes and notably upon seals, the ways to display coats of arms remain very few. There are no known examples of noble arms upon pieces of furniture, textiles, bookplates and other objects, largely decorated with coats of arms in Western and Central Europe. We can mention here the portrait of Dimitrie Ralet (1789), a work decorated with the correctly-rendered and coloured coat of arms of the sitter – however, this portrait was apparently painted in Transylvania⁶⁴, and knowing that the easel portrait was rarely met with the art of the Romanian Principalities until the beginning of the 19th century⁶⁵, this particular use of a coat of arms was nothing but an exception (Fig. 25-26).

⁶² Ferdinand Bartsch, *Les timbres des armoiries des familles de Moldavie et de Valachie*, in *Recueil du 11^e Congrès international des sciences généalogique et héraldique*, Liège, 29 mai - 3 juin 1972, Liège, 1972, p. 68 and fig. 4 (letter dated 12 July 1804).

⁶³ *Condica documentelor ce adeverează genealoghia familiei Miclescu, împreună cu arborul spiței și stema care pe răzământul cercetării s-au întărit și prin hrisov domnesc*, s. 1., 1841 (private collection); more on this manuscript and its coat of arms at Andrei Pippidi, *Genealogia familiei Miclescu, după un izvor necunoscut*, in *ArhGen*, VI (XI) (1999), 1-4, p. 157-167 (photography by Lucian-Valeriu Lefter). The same process of continuously changing the coats of arms was found regarding the arms of Palade / Paladi family, since the last years of the 18th century – Sorin Iftimi, *Observații privitoare la ctitorii mănăstirii Sfântul Sava din Iași*, in *Contribuții privitoare la istoria relațiilor dintre Țările Române și bisericile răsăritene în secolele XIX-XIX*, Petronel Zahariuc (editor), 2009, p. 115.

⁶⁴ Sorin Iftimi, *Vechile blazoane...*, p. 16-17, 42-43.

⁶⁵ Andrei Cornea, „Primitivii” picturii românești moderne, București, 1980, p. 20-21.

Fig. 25.

Fig. 26.

The Moldavian noble class of the time expressed its status and prestige through the appearance of the costume, the latter being deeply influenced by the fashion of the Ottoman capital and permitting, by the instrumentality of shapes, colours and decorations, to place exactly the bearer's position upon the social scale⁶⁶. From the point of view of the local elite, the prestige was mainly expressed by wealthy costumes, expensive horses, large households etc. Compared with these attributes, reflecting the Oriental taste and mentalities of the noble class, the use of coats of arms remained obviously secondary, and the situation remained unchanged until the late 18th - the early 19th centuries, when the increasing interest for genealogy⁶⁷ and the contact with the noble officers of the Russian and Austrian armies of occupation⁶⁸ determined the Moldavian and Wallachian boyars to think a little more about heraldry. This long-term process eventually led to the "stabilization" of a large series of coats of arms belonging to the upper and middle noble class, process evolving under the strong influence of the French heraldic art⁶⁹ but transcending the timelines of this study. During this late Phanariot age, the best example of genealogical awareness mirrored using the mechanism of heraldry is the 1813 genealogy of the Balș family (Fig. 27)⁷⁰.

⁶⁶ Constanța Vintilă-Ghițulescu, «*La mode vient de Constantinople*»: *Les boyards roumains entre Orient et Occident (XVIII^e siècle)*, in *EB*, 2009, p. 113-117.

⁶⁷ G. Bezviconi, *Cercetări genealogice românești (I)*, in *ArhGenAII*, IV (1992), 1-2, p. 517-519.

⁶⁸ Dan Cernovodeanu, *Știința...*, p. 173.

⁶⁹ Idem, *Les influences de l'art héraldique français sur l'art héraldique roumain*, in *Hidalguía*, Año XXXI, Septiembre-Octubre 1983, Num. 180, p. 696-697.

⁷⁰ Reproduction after *Familiiile boierești din Moldova și Țara Românească. Enciclopedie istorică, genealogică și biografică*, coordonator and coauthor Mihai Dim. Sturdza, vol. I, 2004, p. 615.

Fig. 27.

Tracing someone's ancestry was not a novelty in the Romanian Principalities, today's archives containing an important number of genealogies regarding all the social layers. These documents were always compiled for legal purposes, in order to demonstrate rights over land⁷¹. However, starting with the last years of the 18th century, several families of the Moldavian noble class – and not the most wealthy! (Hâncu – 1796, Bădărău – 1812, Hermeziu – 1814, Kațiki – 1816 etc.) – started to elaborate pedigrees comparable with those of the European nobility⁷². Compared with other previous or subsequent similar instances, the 1813 document is eloquent for the growing interest for heraldry and genealogy of the Moldavian high society of the period. Ordered by one of the most influential and wealthiest families

⁷¹ Mihai Sorin Radulescu, *Genealogia Românească. Istoric și bibliografie*, Brăila, 2000, p. 9.

⁷² Maria Dogaru, *op. cit.*, p. 13.

of the time, and reflecting the Romantic vision on the genealogy, the pedigree was illustrated with shields alluding to each past or living member of the family, the shields becoming more and more complicated, as to include the arms of the related families (the graphic design was insured by the German architect Johann Freywald, assisted by two Moldavians, the *sluger* Constantin Leondari and the clerk Toader Gaşpar). Based on historical documents rigorously recorded, the document got all the validations which were possible to collect in the small Principality of Moldavia: from the prince Scarlat Alexandru Calimah (Callimachi), from the members of the *Divan* (the Princely Council), from the Austrian and Russian envoys to Iaşi and, last but not least, from all the living members of the family⁷³.

After reviewing the main features of the heraldic phenomenon during the Phanariot age, our analysis will focus on the aspect itself of the coats of arms, regarding the construction of the achievements. The lecturers already noticed the multiple types used by the Moldavian boyars, and if we compare these with other achievements, we can draw the following conclusions, tellingly for a self-assumed heraldry:

1. Using coat of arms was not a privilege of the upper nobility; for instance, a small co-proprietor of land ('răzeş'), like a certain Panaioghie Ştefan of Doljeşti, used in 1765 a seal containing a shield with a simple noble crown (**Fig. 28**)⁷⁴.

Fig. 28.

2. Women (**Fig. 29** – example from a 1766 document, sealed by Zamfira, widow of the former great *jitnicer* Vasile Tănase)⁷⁵ and members of the clergy (**Fig. 30** – example with the arms of the archpriest Mihail Strilbiţchi, upon a woodcut depicting St John of Damascus, from the *Octoih* of 1786)⁷⁶, equally used coats of arms.

⁷³ Ibidem, p. 18-25 (importance for genealogy), 26-41 (importance for genealogy), 47-52 (graphic design), 53-55 (validation of the document).

⁷⁴ Maria Dogaru, *Sigiliile, mărturii ale trecutului istoric*, Bucureşti, 1976, p. 252 and fig. 289 (document of 21 January 1765).

⁷⁵ BAR, *Documente istorice*, CXXXIII/199.

⁷⁶ Ioan Bianu, Nerva Hodoş, *Bibliografia românească veche*, vol. II (1716-1808), Bucureşti, 1910, p. 314, fig. 310

3. The local elite was aware that the coat of arms is based on the shield, however there are enough instances in which the heraldic symbol appears as rendered without the contour of a shield, as in the curious 1789 seal-impression of Gheorghe Cuza (**Fig. 31**)⁷⁷.

Fig. 29.

Fig. 30.

Fig. 31.

4. The charges of the inner surface of the shield were parts of the bestiary (generally lion and eagle, rarely fish, reptiles, and monsters), symbols related to firmament, flowers and trees, rarely inanimate objects. The ordinaries and subordinaries were rarely met, except for seal impressions like the three bendlets of the 1752 achievement of the family Razu (**Fig. 32**)⁷⁸, or the bend sinister of the 1714 achievement of Tudora, daughter of Miron Costin and widow of the *spătar* Gligoraș (**Fig. 33**)⁷⁹. Abstract charges were also infrequent, as was the *Hausmarke* included in the 1813 heraldic seal of Iliana Bantaș (**Fig. 34**)⁸⁰. Shield partitions were quite rare, as in the above-mentioned sepulchral coat of arms of Neculai Stratulat, containing a quarterly shield. Rarely, arms were canting, as in the 1715 seal impression of Anița, widow of Aslan *cămănariul* (**Fig. 35**)⁸¹, the lion of the seal alluding the Turkish husband's family name ('Aslan' = lion)⁸².

⁷⁷ Gheorghe Ghibănescu, *Cuzeștii*, Iași, 1912 (excerpt from „Surete și izvoade”, VII), cover page; the monogram gives the inscription „GHEO(RGHE) K(U)Z(A)”. We can also mention here the achievement belonging to a member of Palade family, situated in the Church of St Sava of Iași (a mantle charged with the lateral-view of the church), all being supported by two lions guardant – Sorin Ifțimi, *Observații...*, p. 115 and fig. 8.

⁷⁸ BAR, *Documente istorice*, XIII/151 (document of 25 June 1752).

⁷⁹ BAR, *Documente istorice*, II/300 (document of 21 April 1714).

⁸⁰ BAR, *Documente istorice*, LXIV/84 (document of 17 January 1813).

⁸¹ BAR, *Documente istorice*, CXVI/5 (document of 27 March 1715).

⁸² Radu Rosetti, *Hatmanul Alecu Aslan (1804-1884)*, in *Familiiile boierești din Moldova și Țara Românească...*, 2004, p. 144.

Fig. 32.

Fig. 33.

Fig. 34.

Fig. 35.

5. The shield had above it a crown or a helmet, on its turn the helmet being crowned or not, with a crest or without it, all at the armiger's choice. Helmets and crests are quite rare⁸³, however there are interesting examples, such as the 1782 seal impression of a certain *pitar* Costache, where the shield containing initials (?) has above it a helmet with a typical Germanic crest: a pair of eagle's wings (Fig. 36)⁸⁴.

Fig. 36.

⁸³ Ferdinand Bartsch, *op. cit.*, p. 68.

⁸⁴ BAR, *Documente istorice*, II/232 (document of 7 May 1782).

6. Generally, the local boyars used open crowns with three visible leaves, as in the seal of the *paharnic* Dimitrie Bogdan (**Fig. 37**)⁸⁵. Besides these crowns, which were typical for the arms of the European untitled nobility, the first decades of the 19th century brought the practice to use different rank crowns⁸⁶ and notably the countly type – but only for twenty or thirty families which composed the ‘top’ nobility of the realm – as it was the Balș family, as indicated by the 1813 genealogy (**Fig. 38**)⁸⁷. (Only a very small number of Moldavian and Wallachian families received the foreign title of a count, the use of the countly being assumed, notably in the 19th century, by families having no rights to such a style, but being only similar with the first lineages from the points of view of social status and fortune.)⁸⁸ On the other hand, as the local knowledge of heraldry was lacking, the boyars also used curious achievements such as the 1765 heraldic seal of a certain captain Mihail Talpă, displaying upon the shield – without any reason! – a full princely crown (**Fig. 39**)⁸⁹.

Fig. 37.

Fig. 38.

Fig. 39.

7. The use of supporters remained at the armiger’s choice, the most common example being a pair of lions – as is found upon the 1798 heraldic seal of a certain Gheorghe Costandin, brother of Enache captain of *lefegii* (**Fig. 40**)⁹⁰. Exceptionally, the unique supporter could be met with, as in the 1779 heraldic seal of the great *paharnic* Nicolae Cantacuzino (**Fig. 41**)⁹¹, with the Byzantine double-headed eagle having a shield of St George, probably alluding the claims of this

⁸⁵ Dan Cernovodeanu, *Știința...*, pl. CIII, fig. 4.

⁸⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 68.

⁸⁷ Maria Dogaru, *Un armorial...*, p. 27, fig. 2.

⁸⁸ Dan Cernovodeanu, *Știința...*, p. 175. Examples of Romanian families which received the title of a count at idem, *Evoluția...*, p. 275.

⁸⁹ BAR, *Documente istorice*, XXXVIII/69 (document of 1 May 1765).

⁹⁰ BAR, *Documente istorice*, XXXVII/147 (document of 7 March 1798).

⁹¹ BAR, *Documente istorice*, CXXI/2 (document of 6 June 1779).

lineage on the Great Mastership of the Constantinian Order⁹². Anyway, having an achievement with supporters was not an indication that the armiger had a better standing on the social ladder.

Fig. 40.

Fig. 41.

8. More than sure inspired by the Moldavian princely coats of arms, the use of a mantle around the shield remain exceptional, as in the 1819 heraldic seal of the great *hatman* Constantin Paladi (Fig. 42)⁹³.

Fig. 42.

⁹² Sorin Iftimi, *Reprezentări heraldice în arhiva Cantacuzinilor: Cartea de Aur a Ordinului Constantinian al Sfântului Gheorghe*, in *De la fictiv la real. Imaginea, imaginarul, imagologia*, Andi Mihalache, Silvia Marin-Barutchieff (coordonatori), Iași, 2010, p. 599-617

⁹³ Dan Cernovodeanu, *Știința...*, pl. CIV, fig. 1 (reproduction after the seal impression belonging to the collection †Jean Nicolas Mănescu).

9. The mottoes remained rather less known in the noble Moldavian coats of arms of the period⁹⁴; an exception can be met by examining the sphragistics of the boyars Costache, of which the pair of heraldic seals from the late 18th – the early 19th century – belonging to the same family, containing the same coat of arms differenced by the presence of the armiger's name, upon one seal, and the motto "CURA QUIETEM" (Fig. 43)⁹⁵.

Fig. 43.

10. The display of orders and medals was exceptional, because the number of Moldavians decorated by foreign rulers in the timelines of our study was very small. However, we identified the example of the funerals coat of arms of Manole (Emanoil) Balș (†1812), from St Demetrius Church of Iași (Fig. 44)⁹⁶. Belonging to the series of arms with multiple quarters – as attested by the above-mentioned 1813 genealogy of Balș family, Manole's shield was decorated with an affronté barred-helmet, a panoply of military trophies and the imperial St Vladimir Order, suspended from its ribbon – all alluding to his career as a *polcovník* (colonel) in the Russian army⁹⁷.

Fig. 44.

⁹⁴ Maria Dogaru, *Devizele în heraldica românească*, in *RA*, LXIX (1992), nr. 2, p. 195-217.

⁹⁵ BAR, *Documente istorice*, LXXXV/159-160. Taken from Vergil's *Aeneid*, 4.5, and having the meaning "vigilance ensures tranquillity", the motto refers the crest of the coat of arms, depicting a crane in its vigilance.

⁹⁶ Tudor-Radu Tiron, *Despre folosirea decorațiilor în stemele boierilor din Moldova și Țara Românească (în perioada domniilor regulamentare)*, in *MN*, XVII (2005), p. 90.

⁹⁷ Maria Dogaru, *Un armorial...*, p. 91.

11. Regarding the relation between heraldry and art, it would be an exaggeration to allege the existence of a heraldic style in the Phanariot Moldavia; despite several minuses and regardless the kind of representation, the achievements analysed so far were vigorously rendered, some of them being drawn with elegance. The lecturer may notice the difference between a heraldic seal like the one used by an unidentified member of the old family Tăutul (**Fig. 45**)⁹⁸ and the one due to the great *vistier* Matei Cantacuzino, used in 1785 (**Fig. 46**)⁹⁹.

Fig. 45.

Fig. 46.

Despite the obvious quality differentiation, which is eloquent for the distinction of fortune and social prestige between the members of the aforementioned boyar families, both the achievements have the elements perfectly perceivable, indicating the viability of the local usage of the noble coats of arms during the Phanariot age. On the other hand, ordering some object to a skilled and learned artist doesn't mean that the coat of arms issued from his hands would be equally well-rendered. For instance, it is obvious that the carver who executed the 1782 gravestone of Lupu Balș, from St Demetrius Church of Iași (**Fig. 47**)¹⁰⁰, was a very gifted artist, as proven by his knowledge of the Late Baroque, as well as of the Oriental decoration. When rendering the coat of arms itself, the artist chose an outdated shield having a Gothic appearance, charged by the family eight-pointed star displayed without elegance, the shield being encircled with two palm branches and carrying something like a rank crown¹⁰¹, all equally unaesthetically rendered. It is clear that the family commissioned the work to a good artist, however the latter was obviously less informed about the way to appropriately display a heraldic achievement.

⁹⁸ Ferdinand Bartsch, *op. cit.*, fig. 2 (reproduction after the seal impression belonging to the collection ȚJean Nicolas Mănescu).

⁹⁹ BAR, *Documente istorice*, XXII/234 (document of 9 October 1785).

¹⁰⁰ N. Iorga, *op. cit.*, fig. 1.000.

¹⁰¹ The crown has three visible leaves or flowers, intercalated by two groups of two pearls – a formula reminding us of the so-called “old type marquis crowns” (with the groups of three pearls displayed in a row, and not as a trefoil).

Fig. 47.

The achievements analysed here allow the researcher to follow some of the basic functions of heraldry: the *need to distinguish individuals*; the *need to proclaim rights and obligations*; the *need to embellish objects and monuments*.

Although impossible to compare with the level reached by the Western and Central European heraldry, the local use of arms during the Phanariot age was a part of continuity, from the mediaeval times to the modern era. Yet, from all points of view, this use of arms meant a transitory phase, being chronologically superposed with the historical bibliography called the Pre-modern period, so an *interval placed from many points of view between two ages*. It is interesting to notice that during the approached period the coats of arms were used by the boyars from all layers, but the use is still hesitant. By the end of the period, the achievements become more correct and stabilize, but their use passes almost exclusively on the account of the great boyars.

The geographical location of the Romanian Principalities caused various influences upon the local heraldry. If a single influence – namely the Polish one –

occurred in the 14th-16th centuries, coinciding with the flourishing of the Moldavian medieval state, during the Phanariot period several influences came together in relation with the local heraldry, the result having a certain *on ne sait quoi*: neither Germanic (as proved by the moderate use of crests), nor Polish (hence the preference for the concrete figures, to the detriment of the abstract ones that constitute a particularity of the Polish noble arms), and not even Transylvanian (because of the avoidance of warrior compositions, which are so particular to this land). The Levant seems to be more present, if we take into account the overloaded, plummy appearance of many compositions, of which some had a theatrical air, making one think of the coats of arms of the Italian Peninsula. This mixture of influences, resulted from the artist's qualification and knowledge, but also from the client's taste and ideas, determined the specific appearance of the Moldavian noble heraldry: *between Western and Eastern models the local elite always found a middle way to express its 'ego', using the resources offered by heraldry.*

The information mentioned above denotes another image of the local heraldic phenomenon. The bibliography knows different authors who gave very little credit to the use of arms by the local elites, as Ștefan D. Grecianu (1825-1908) and Neculai Grămadă (1892-1961). For instance, more than one century ago, the first asked rhetorically: "...what kind of flags, achievements, emblems and coats of arms used our forefathers when being at war, upon palaces, churches, in peacetime, when mourning, when rejoicing, when distinguishing in public area or in the battlefield? (...) Which are the images that we know for sure? Where are recorded and explained such coats of arms belonging to us? We had no idea about all these..."¹⁰²; the author argued that the lack of political stability and the law precarity, notably during the Phanariot age, retarded the general use of heraldry in the Principality¹⁰³. After half a century, the second author wrote an analysis on the "heraldic establishment", drawing the conclusion that we had no such thing, given the fact that we had no Western-like nobility and no armorial grants were recorded, while instances in which a boyar received a foreign grant were considered to be extraneous, as well as the achievements of the Phanariot families, "...who brought their coats of arms from Byzantium..."¹⁰⁴. Mentioning these sceptical opinions is not without importance; the good faith of both authors is undeniable, however the studies published in the last decades and the clear evidence of the preserved heraldic achievements offering an adequate image of the local "heraldic establishment". *Primo*, the obvious continuity – generally speaking! – of the use of arms in the Romanian Principalities denotes that the lack of political or legal stability had no influence over the armorial practise. *Secundo*, the practice of

¹⁰² Ștefan D. Grecianu, *Eraldica română. Actele privitoare la stabilirea armeriilor oficiale, cu planșe și vocabular*, București, 1900, p. L.

¹⁰³ *Ibidem*, p. XIX, XLI.

¹⁰⁴ Nicolai Grămadă, *A existat la Români instituția eraldică?*, in *SCI*, vol. XIX (vol. II, serie nouă) (1946), p. 26-32.

conferring arms is indeed characteristic for the Western and Central-European heraldry, however this is not an exclusive rule, lots of families using arms with no written grant or confirmation. The example of the Transylvanian conferred and self-assumed arms is clear enough in this particular issue¹⁰⁵. *Tertio*, thinking that all the noble coats of arms should have a given meaning constitutes an outdated vision; in fact, only a small part of the coats of arms ever used were actually associated with some story or a legend¹⁰⁶, such instances being often doubtful for today's researchers. *Quarto*, the Western and Central-European heraldry contains an important number of grants of arms addressed to foreign subjects, the best example being the diplomas issued, century after century, by the Habsburg monarchs, to people living outside their jurisdiction; this was also the case of the grants directed to the Moldavian or Wallachian subjects, such grants being issued outside the Romanian Principalities, but being intended to be use inside them. *Quinto*, the variety of the armorial use in the Principality has been recently proven by the researcher Ștefan S. Gorovei, into a study dealing with mediaeval Romanian noble heraldry, which conclusions are also valid for our timelines: "...What percent of our documentary and artistic patrimony has been preserved? A coat of arms is not engraved upon one only silverware item, it is not painted upon one only manuscript, it is not decorating one only bell, it is not carved upon one only commemorative inscription. (...) We should therefore admit from the very beginning that many objects having this kind of decoration have been lost – probably for ever..."¹⁰⁷. Therefore, what we know about the Moldavian and Wallachian noble heraldry of the Phanariot age is only a part of the information, and if we took into account all the unpublished material (sphragistic but not only), conserved into the public and private archives, as well as in the museums, and if we also consider all the achievements destroyed or lost during the last two centuries, we would have a much more better image on the complexity of the noble heraldry of the Phanariot age.

Freely assumed and used, the coats of arms of the Phanariot age often denote social mechanisms, political ambitions and genealogical motivations. On the other hand, the absence of chromatics, the absence of a specific vocabulary, as well as the absence of any concern about approaching heraldry in a scholarly manner, all these demonstrate the 'fragile', and yet perfectly valid character of the Moldavian noble heraldry of the 18th century – the beginning of the 19th century.

¹⁰⁵ Tudor-Radu Tiron, *Despre dreptul la stemă în Transilvania secolului XVII*, in *SMIM*, XXIV (2006), p. 224-226.

¹⁰⁶ Gourdon de Genouillac, *Les mystères du blason, de la noblesse et de la féodalité*, E. Dentu, Paris, 1868, p. 54-84.

¹⁰⁷ Ștefan S. Gorovei, *Cu privire la heraldica medievală românească*, in *ArhGen*, II (VII) (1995), 1-2, p. 274.

The noble heraldry of the pre-modern Moldavia

Abstract

Attested upon the oldest preserved documents, the noble seals were using coats of arms, following Western influences. Less developed than in the rest of Europe, the local noble heraldry had an uninterrupted evolution, also during the Phanariots age. Only a part of the great noble lineages displayed coats of arms, while the armorial usage was rarely met with the lower nobility. Having interesting particularities, the local heraldry reflected the social status of the elites of the Principality of Moldavia.

Keywords: Principality of Moldavia; Moldavian noble class; coats of arms; seals; Phanariot age.

ABREVIERI

<i>AARMSI</i>	= Analele Academiei Române, Memoriile Secțiunii Istorice
<i>AARMSL</i>	= Analele Academiei Române, Memoriile Secțiunii Literare
<i>AARPAD</i>	= „Analele Academiei Române”, seria II, București, 1879-1916
<i>AA.SS.</i>	= <i>Acta Sanctorum</i> , ed. Bollandisti, III ^a ediție, Parigi 1863-1870
<i>AB</i>	= Arhivele Basarabiei
<i>ACNSAS</i>	= Arhivele Consiliului Național pentru Studierea Arhivelor Securității
<i>AE</i>	= L'Année Epigraphique, Paris
<i>AIR</i>	= Arhiva Istorică a României
<i>AIAC</i>	= Anuarul Institutului de Istorie și Arheologie Cluj
<i>AIIAI</i>	= Anuarul Institutului de Istorie și Arheologie „A. D. Xenopol”, Iași
<i>AIIC</i>	= Anuarul Institutului de Istorie Cluj
<i>AIINC</i>	= Anuarul Institutului de Istorie Națională, Cluj
<i>AIIX</i>	= Anuarul Institutului de Istorie „A. D. Xenopol”, Iași
<i>ALIL</i>	= Anuarul de Lingvistică și Istorie Literară, Iași
<i>ALMA</i>	= <i>Archivum Latinitatis Medii Aevi</i> . Genève.
<i>AMAE</i>	= Arhiva Ministerului Afacerilor Externe
<i>AmAnthr</i>	= American Anthropologist, New Series, Published by Wiley on behalf of the American Anthropological Association
<i>AMM</i>	= Acta Moldaviae Meridionalis, Vaslui
<i>AMMB</i>	= Arhiva Mitropoliei Moldovei și Bucovinei, Iași
<i>AMN</i>	= Acta Musei Napocensis
<i>AMR</i>	= Arhivele Militare Române
<i>AMS</i>	= Anuarul Muzeului din Suceava
<i>ANB</i>	= Arhivele Naționale, București
<i>ANC</i>	= Arhivele Naționale. Serviciul Județean Cluj
<i>ANDMB</i>	= Arhivele Naționale. Direcția Municipiului București
<i>ANG</i>	= Arhivele Naționale. Serviciul Județean Galați
<i>ANI</i>	= Arhivele Naționale, Iași
<i>ANIC</i>	= Arhivele Naționale Istorice Centrale
<i>ANRM</i>	= Arhivele Naționale ale Republicii Moldova, Chișinău
<i>ANRW</i>	= Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischen Welt, Berlin-New York
<i>ANSMB</i>	= Arhivele Naționale. Serviciul Municipiului București
<i>ANV</i>	= Arhivele Naționale, Vaslui
<i>AO</i>	= Arhivele Olteniei
<i>AP</i>	= Analele Putnei
<i>APH</i>	= Acta Poloniae Historica, Varșovia
<i>AR</i>	= Arhiva Românească
<i>ArchM</i>	= Archiva Moldaviae”, Iași
<i>ArhGen</i>	= Arhiva Genealogică
<i>„Arhiva”</i>	= „Arhiva”. Organul Societății Științifice și Literare, Iași
<i>ArhMold</i>	= Arheologia Moldovei
<i>ASRR</i>	= Arhiva Societății Române de Radiodifuziune
<i>AȘUI</i>	= Analele Științifice ale Universității „Al. I. Cuza”, Iași
<i>ATS</i>	= Ancient Textile Series, Oxbow Books, Oxford și Oakville
<i>AUB</i>	= Analele Universității „București”
<i>BAR</i>	= Biblioteca Academiei Române
<i>BArchB</i>	= Bundesarchiv Berlin

<i>BAR int. ser.</i>	= British Archaeological Reports, International Series
<i>BBR</i>	= Buletinul Bibliotecii Române
<i>BCIR</i>	= Buletinul Comisiei Istorice a României
<i>BCMI</i>	= Buletinul Comisiei Monumentelor Istorice
<i>BCU-Iași</i>	= Biblioteca Centrală Universitară, Iași
<i>BE</i>	= Bulletin Epigraphique
<i>BF</i>	= Byzantinische Forschungen, Amsterdam
<i>BMI</i>	= Buletinul Monumentelor Istorice
<i>BMIM</i>	= București. Materiale de istorie și muzeografie
<i>BNB</i>	= Biblioteca Națională București
<i>BNJ</i>	= Byzantinisch-Neugriechische Jahrbücher
<i>BOR</i>	= Biserica Ortodoxă Română
<i>BS</i>	= Balkan Studies
<i>BSNR</i>	= Buletinul Societății Numismatice Române
<i>ByzSlav</i>	= Byzantinoslavica
<i>CA</i>	= Cercetări arheologice
<i>CAI</i>	= Caiete de Antropologie Istorice
<i>CB</i>	= Cahiers balkaniques
<i>CC</i>	= Codrul Cosminului, Suceava (ambele serii)
<i>CCAR</i>	= Cronica cercetărilor arheologice din România, CIMEC, București
<i>CCCh</i>	= <i>Corpus Christianorum</i> , Turnhout
<i>CChSG</i>	= <i>Corpus Christianorum. Series Graeca</i>
<i>CDM</i>	= <i>Catalogul documentelor moldovenești din Arhivele Centrale de Stat</i> , București, vol. I-V; supl. I.
<i>CDȚR</i>	= <i>Catalogul documentelor Țării Românești din Arhivele Statului</i> , București, vol. II-VIII, 1974-2006
<i>CI</i>	= Cercetări istorice (ambele serii)
<i>CIL</i>	= <i>Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum</i> , Berlin
<i>CL</i>	= Cercetări literare
<i>CN</i>	= Cercetări Numismatice
<i>CNA</i>	= Cronica Numismatică și Arheologică, București
<i>CSCO</i>	= <i>Corpus Scriptorum Christianorum Orientalium</i> , Louvain
<i>CSPAMI</i>	= Centrul de Studii și Păstrare a Arhivelor Militare Centrale, Pitești
<i>CT</i>	= Columna lui Traian, București
<i>Cv.L</i>	= Convorbiri literare (ambele serii)
<i>„Dacia”, N.S.</i>	= Dacia. Nouvelle Série, Revue d'archéologie et d'histoire ancienne, București
<i>DANIC</i>	= Direcția Arhivelor Naționale Istorice Centrale
<i>DGAS</i>	= Direcția Generală a Arhivelor Statului
<i>DI</i>	= Diplomatarium Italicum
<i>DIR</i>	= <i>Documente privind istoria României</i>
<i>DIRRI</i>	= <i>Documente privind Istoria României. Războiul pentru Independență</i>
<i>DTN</i>	= <i>Din trecutul nostru</i> , Chișinău
<i>DOP</i>	= Dumbarton Oaks Papers
<i>DRH</i>	= <i>Documenta Romaniae Historica</i>
<i>EB</i>	= Études Balkaniques
<i>EBPB</i>	= Études byzantines et post-byzantines
<i>EpigrAnat</i>	= Epigraphica Anatolica, Münster
<i>Gerión</i>	= Gerión. Revista de Historia Antigua, Madrid
<i>GB</i>	= Glasul Bisericii
<i>GLK</i>	= <i>Grammatici Latini Keil</i>
<i>„Hierasus”</i>	= <i>Hierasus</i> . Anuarul Muzeului Județean Botoșani, Botoșani
<i>HM</i>	= Heraldica Moldaviae, Chișinău
<i>HU</i>	= Historia Urbana, Sibiu

- HUI = Historia Universitatis Iassensis, Iași
 IDR = *Inscripțiile din Dacia romană*, Bucurști-Paris
 IDRE = *Inscriptions de la Dacie romaine. Inscriptions externes concernant l'histoire de la Dacie*, I-II, Bucarest, 1996, 2000
 IGLN = *Inscriptions grecques et latines de Novae*, Bordeaux
 IGLR = *Inscripțiile grecești și latine din secolele IV-XIII descoperite în România*, București, 1976
 ILLPecs = *Instrumenta Inscripta Latina. Das römische Leben im Spiegel der Kleininschriften*, Pecs, 1991
 ILB = *Inscriptiones Latinae in Bulgaria repertae. Inscriptiones inter Oescum et Iatrum repertae*, Sofia, 1989
 ILD = *Inscripții latine din Dacia*, București
 ILN = *Inscriptions latines de Novae*, Poznan
 ILLPRON = *Inscriptionum Lapidarium Latinarum Provinciae Norici usque ad annum MCMLXXXIV repertarum indices*, Berlin, 1986
 ILS = *Inscriptiones Latinae Selectae*, 1892
 IN = „Ioan Neculce”. Buletinul Muzeului Municipal Iași
 ISM = *Inscripțiile din Scythia Minor grecești și latine*, București, vol. I-III, 1983-1999
 JGO = *Jahrbücher für Geschichte Osteuropas*
 JL = *Junimea literară*
 JRS = *The Journal of Roman studies*, London
 LR = *Limba română*
 MA = *Memoria Antiquitatis*, Piatra Neamț
 MCA = *Materiale și cercetări arheologice*
 MEF = *Moldova în epoca feudalismului*, vol. I-XII, 1961-2012, Chișinău
 MGH = *Monumenta Germaniae Historica inde ab anno Christi quingentesimo usque ad annum millesimum et quingentesimum auspiciis societatis aperiendis fontibus rerum Germanicarum medii aevi*, Berlin 1877-
 MI = *Magazin istoric*, București
 MIM = *Materiale de istorie și muzeografie*
 MM = *Mitropolia Moldovei*
 MMS = *Mitropolia Moldovei și Sucevei*
 MN = *Muzeul Național*, București
 MO = *Mitropolia Olteniei*
 MOF = *Monitorul Oficial al României*
 NEH = *Nouvelles études d'histoire*
 OI = *Opțiuni istoriografice*, Iași
 OPEL = *Onomasticon provinciarum Europae latinarum*, vol. I-IV, Budapesta-Viena, 1994-2002
 PG = J.-P. Migne, *Patrologiae cursus completus, Series Graeca*, Paris
 RA = *Revista arhivelor*
 RBAR = *Revista Bibliotecii Academiei Române*, București
 RC = *Revista catolică*
 RdI = *Revista de istorie*
 REByz = *Revue des Études Byzantines*
 RER = *Revue des études roumaines*
 RESEE = *Revue des études Sud-Est européennes*
 RHSEE = *Revue historique de Sud-Est européen*
 RI = *Revista istorică (ambele serii)*
 RIAF = *Revista pentru istorie, arheologie și filologie*
 RIB = *Roman Inscriptions of Britain*, Londra
 RIM = *Revista de Istorie a Moldovei*, Chișinău
 RIR = *Revista istorică română*, București

<i>RIS</i>	= Revista de istorie socială, Iași
<i>RITL</i>	= Revista de istorie și teorie literară
<i>RJMH</i>	= The Romanian Journal of Modern History, Iași
<i>RM</i>	= Revista muzeelor
<i>RMM-MIA</i>	= Revista muzeelor și monumentelor, seria Monumente istorice și de artă
<i>RMR</i>	= Revista Medicală Română
<i>RRH</i>	= Revue roumaine d'histoire
<i>RRHA</i>	= Revue roumaine de l'histoire de l'art
<i>RRHA-BA</i>	= Revue Roumaine d'Histoire de l'Art. Série Beaux Arts
<i>RSIAB</i>	= Revista Societății istorice și arheologice bisericești, Chișinău
<i>Rsl</i>	= Romanoslavica
<i>SAI</i>	= Studii și Articole de Istorie
<i>SCB</i>	= Studii și cercetări de bibliologie
<i>SCh</i>	= <i>Sources Chrétiennes</i> , Paris
<i>SCIA</i>	= Studii și cercetări de istoria artei
<i>SCIM</i>	= Studii și cercetări de istorie medie
<i>SCIV/SCIVA</i>	= Studii și cercetări de istorie veche (și arheologie)
<i>SCN</i>	= Studii și Cercetări Numismatice, București
<i>SCȘI</i>	= Studii și cercetări științifice, Istorie
<i>SEER</i>	= The Slavonic and East European Review
<i>SHA</i>	= <i>Scriptores Historiae Augustae</i>
<i>SJAN</i>	= Serviciul Județean al Arhivelor Naționale
<i>SMIC</i>	= Studii și materiale de istorie contemporană, București
<i>SMIM</i>	= Studii și materiale de istorie medie, București
<i>SOF</i>	= Südost-Forschungen, München
<i>ST</i>	= Studii Teologice, București
<i>StAntArh</i>	= <i>Studia Antiqua et Archaeologica</i> , Iași
<i>T&MBYZ</i>	= <i>Travaux et Mémoires du Centre de recherches d'histoire et de civilisation byzantines</i>
<i>ThD</i>	= Thraco-Dacica, București
<i>TR</i>	= Transylvanian Review, Cluj-Napoca
<i>TV</i>	= Teologie și viața, Iași
<i>ZPE</i>	= Zeitschrift für Papyralogie und Epigraphik
<i>ZSL</i>	= Zeitschrift für Siebenbürgische Landeskunde